

Figure S1 NJ tree drawn by MEGA7 (Kumar et al 2016, Mol Biol Evol 33:1870–1874; K2P model) of Cytb sequences from eels

Table S1 Reads after each step

Sites	Samples Replicate	Raw read	Merged	Quality filter	Denoise
Left bank	Replicate 1	291,355	276,913 (95.04%)	276,788 (95.00%)	270,582 (92.87%)
	Replicate 2	316,222	300,284 (94.96%)	300,113 (94.91%)	293,580 (92.84%)
Center of flow	Replicate 1	269,549	256,423 (95.13%)	256,276 (95.08%)	250,054 (92.77%)
	Replicate 2	307,082	289,167 (94.17%)	288,993 (94.11%)	282,687 (92.06%)
Right bank	Replicate 1	320,925	303,460 (94.56%)	303,277 (94.50%)	296,789 (92.48%)
	Replicate 2	291,289	275,418 (94.55%)	275,237 (94.49%)	269,014 (92.35%)
NC	-	7,617	6,944 (91.16%)	6,915 (90.78%)	6,511 (85.48%)

Table S2 Sequence alignment of Cytb from eel specimens and reference sequences

	5	15	25	35	45	55
22eel102_Hap01	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel110_Hap02	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel103-04_Hap03	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel112_Hap04	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel105_08-09_11	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel116-17_Hap06	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel107_Hap07	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel101_Hap08	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
22eel106_Hap09	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_japonica_AB038	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_luzonensis_AB4	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_australis_aust	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_australis_schm	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_bicolor_bicolo	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_bicolor_pacifi	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_malgumora_AP00	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGACGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_celebesensis_A	ATGGCAAGCC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_dieffenbachii_	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_interioris_AP0	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_marmorata_AP00	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_megastoma_AP00	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_mossambica_AP0	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_labiata_AP0072	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_nebulosa_nebul	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_obscura_AP0072	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_reinhardtii_AP	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTC	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_rostrata_AP007	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAATGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_anguilla_KJ564	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT
A_bengalensis_be	ATGGCAAACC	TACGAAAAAC	CCACCCACTT	CTAAAAATTG	CTAACGATGC	CCTAGTGGAT

	65	75	85	95	105	115
22eel102_Hap01	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22eel110_Hap02	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22eel103-04_Hap03	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22eel112_Hap04	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC

22ee105_08-09_11	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22ee116-17_Hap06	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22ee107_Hap07	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	tCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22ee101_Hap08	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGtATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
22ee106_Hap09	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAAtAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
A_japonica_AB038	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
A_luzonensis_AB4	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_australis_aust	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGT
A_australis_schm	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGT
A_bicolor_bicolo	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_bicolor_pacifi	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGT
A_malgumora_AP00	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCACTCCT	TGGATTATGC
A_celebesensis_A	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_dieffenbachii_	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_interioris_AP0	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGT
A_marmorata_AP00	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_megastoma_AP00	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGC
A_mossambica_AP0	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGACTATGT
A_labiata_AP0072	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_nebulosa_nebul	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_obscura_AP0072	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_reinhardtii_AP	CTACCAACCC	CCTCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC
A_rostrata_AP007	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTTCT	AGGATTATGT
A_anguilla_KJ564	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAATAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTTCT	AGGATTATGT
A_bengalensis_be	CTACCAACCC	CATCCAACAT	TTCAGCATGA	TGAAATTTTG	GCTCTCTCCT	AGGATTATGC

....
125	135	145	155	165	175

22ee102_Hap01	CTTATcTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee110_Hap02	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee103-04_Hap03	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee112_Hap04	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee105_08-09_11	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee116-17_Hap06	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee107_Hap07	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee101_Hap08	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
22ee106_Hap09	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_japonica_AB038	CTTATTTTCGC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCAATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_luzonensis_AB4	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTT	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA

A_australis_aust	CTCATCTCAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTATACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_australis_schm	CTCATCTCAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTATACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_bicolor_bicolo	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCGTCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTATACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_bicolor_pacifi	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCGTTAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTATACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_malgumora_AP00	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCCTCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ATTATACATC	AGATATCTCA
A_celebesensis_A	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCGTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_dieffenbachii_	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTATACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_interioris_AP0	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_marmorata_AP00	CTAATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_megastoma_AP00	CTTATCTCCC	AAATAGTTAC	AGGATTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_mossambica_AP0	CTTATCTCTC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGACTGTTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_labiata_AP0072	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_nebulosa_nebul	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_obscura_AP0072	CTTATTTTAC	AAATCGTCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA
A_reinhardtii_AP	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_rostrata_AP007	CTTATTTTAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ATTATACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_anguilla_KJ564	CTTATTTTAC	AAATCCTTAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ATTATACATC	AGACATCTCA
A_bengalensis_be	CTTATCTCAC	AAATCATCAC	AGGACTATTC	CTAGCCATAC	ACTACACATC	AGACATTTCA

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |

185 195 205 215 225 235

22ee102_Hap01	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee110_Hap02	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee103-04_Hap03	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee112_Hap04	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee105_08-09_11	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee116-17_Hap06	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee107_Hap07	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee101_Hap08	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
22ee106_Hap09	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
A_japonica_AB038	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTCATCCGA
A_luzonensis_AB4	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATTTGC	CGAGATGTTA	ACTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGC
A_australis_aust	ACCGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTCA	ACTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGT
A_australis_schm	ACCGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTCA	ACTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGT
A_bicolor_bicolo	ACCGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCATATTTGT	CGAGACGTTA	ACTACGGATG	ACTAATCCGC
A_bicolor_pacifi	ACCGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCATATTTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ACTACGGATG	ACTAATCCGC
A_malgumora_AP00	ACCGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGATGTCA	ACTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGC
A_celebesensis_A	ACCGCCTTCT	CTTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTCA	ATTACGGATG	ATTGATCCGT
A_dieffenbachii_	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ACTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGT

A_interioris_AP0	ACCGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATTTGT	CGAGACGTTA	ACTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGT
A_marmorata_AP00	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATTTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGGTG	ACTAATCCGC
A_megastoma_AP00	ACCGCATTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATTTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGT
A_mossambica_AP0	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTGGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGATGTCA	ACTATGGATG	ATTAATCCGT
A_labiata_AP0072	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGC
A_nebulosa_nebul	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGC
A_obscura_AP0072	ACTGCTTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATTTGC	CGAGATGTAA	ATTACGGATG	ATTAATCCGC
A_reinhardtii_AP	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTGATCCGC
A_rostrata_AP007	ACTGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	TCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTCA	ACTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGC
A_anguilla_KJ564	ACTGCCTTCT	CCTCAGTAGC	TCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTCA	ACTATGGATG	ACTAATTCGC
A_bengalensis_be	ACTGCCTTTT	CCTCAGTAGC	CCACATCTGC	CGAGACGTTA	ATTATGGATG	ATTAATTCGC

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |

245 255 265 275 285 295

22ee102_Hap01	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee110_Hap02	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee103-04_Hap03	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee112_Hap04	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee105_08-09_11	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee116-17_Hap06	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee107_Hap07	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee101_Hap08	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
22ee106_Hap09	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
A_japonica_AB038	AATTTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
A_luzonensis_AB4	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATTTGCC	TATATCTCCA	TATTGCCCGA
A_australis_aust	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TCTACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_australis_schm	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TCTACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_bicolor_bicolo	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCATTCTTC	TTCATTTGTC	TGTACCTTCA	CATCGCCCGA
A_bicolor_pacifi	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCATTCTTC	TTCATTTGTC	TGTACCTTCA	CATCGCCCGA
A_malgumora_AP00	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATTTGCC	TCTACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_celebesensis_A	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTT	TTCATTTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
A_dieffenbachii_	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCATTCTTC	TTTATTTGCC	TCTACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_interioris_AP0	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TATATCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_marmorata_AP00	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTT	TTCATCTGCC	TATACCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_megastoma_AP00	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATCTGCC	TCTACCTACA	CATTGCCCGA
A_mossambica_AP0	AACCTACATG	CAAATGGGAGC	TTCTTCTTC	TTCATCTGCC	TCTACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_labiata_AP0072	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TATATCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_nebulosa_nebul	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TATATCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_obscura_AP0072	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATTTGCC	TGTACCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA

A_reinhardtii_AP	AACTTACATG	CAAACGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTTATTTGTC	TCTACCTGCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_rostrata_AP007	AACCTACATG	CAAATGGGGC	CTCATTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TATACCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_anguilla_KJ564	AACCTACATG	CAAATGGAGC	CTCATTCTTC	TTTATCTGCC	TATACCTCCA	CATTGCCCGA
A_bengalensis_be	AACCTACATG	CAAACGGAGC	CTCCTTCTTC	TTCATTTGCC	TATATCTTCA	CATTGCCCGA

	305	315	325	335	345	355
22ee102_Hap01	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee110_Hap02	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee103-04_Hap03	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee112_Hap04	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee105_08-09_11	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee116-17_Hap06	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee107_Hap07	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee101_Hap08	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
22ee106_Hap09	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_japonica_AB038	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_luzonensis_AB4	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTATAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTGCTATTC
A_australis_aust	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	TGTATTATTC
A_australis_schm	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	TGTATTATTC
A_bicolor_bicolo	GGACTTTACT	ACGGATCGTA	TCTTTATAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_bicolor_pacifi	GGACTTTACT	ACGGATCATA	TCTTTATAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_malgumora_AP00	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	AGTATTATTC
A_celebesensis_A	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_dieffenbachii_	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	CGTATTATTC
A_interioris_AP0	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTGCTATTC
A_marmorata_AP00	GGACTTTACT	ACGGTTCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_megastoma_AP00	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCGTA	CCTTTATAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	TGTATTATTC
A_mossambica_AP0	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	TGTATTATTC
A_labiata_AP0072	GGGCTTTACT	ACGGCTCGTA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGGGT	CGTACTATTC
A_nebulosa_nebul	GGGCTTTACT	ACGGCTCGTA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGGGT	CGTACTATTC
A_obscura_AP0072	GGACTTTACT	ACGGATCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_reinhardtii_AP	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTATAAA	GAGACATGAA	ACATCGGAGT	CGTACTATTC
A_rostrata_AP007	GGACTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	TCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	CGTATTATTC
A_anguilla_KJ564	GGGCTTTACT	ACGGCTCATA	CCTTTACATA	GAAACATGAA	ACATTGGAGT	TGTATTATTC
A_bengalensis_be	GGGCTTTACT	ACGGCTCGTA	CCTTTACAAA	GAAACATGAA	ACATCGGGGT	CGTACTATTC

	365	375	385	395	405	415

22ee102_Hap01	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee110_Hap02	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee103-04_Hap03	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee112_Hap04	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee105_08-09_11	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee116-17_Hap06	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee107_Hap07	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee101_Hap08	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
22ee106_Hap09	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_japonica_AB038	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACTGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_luzonensis_AB4	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_australis_aust	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTGGGA	TACGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCGTTC
A_australis_schm	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTGGGA	TACGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCGTTC
A_bicolor_bicolo	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TACGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_bicolor_pacifi	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TACGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_malgumora_AP00	CTACTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CGTGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_celebesensis_A	CTACTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGG	TACGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_dieffenbachii_	CTGCTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_interioris_AP0	CTACTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_marmorata_AP00	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_megastoma_AP00	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_mossambica_AP0	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTC
A_labiata_AP0072	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTT
A_nebulosa_nebul	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTT
A_obscura_AP0072	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	GATATCATTC
A_reinhardtii_AP	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGGCA	AATATCATTC
A_rostrata_AP007	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGG	TATGTA	TACTTC	CATGAGGACA	GATATCATTC
A_anguilla_KJ564	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTG	TCTTC	CATGAGGACA	GATATCATTC
A_bengalensis_be	CTATTAGTAA	TAATAACAGC	ATTCGTAGGA	TATGTA	TACTCC	CATGAGGACA	AATATCATTT

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |

425 435 445 455 465 475

22ee102_Hap01	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTgC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee110_Hap02	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee103-04_Hap03	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee112_Hap04	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee105_08-09_11	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee116-17_Hap06	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22ee107_Hap07	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA

22eel01_Hap08	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
22eel06_Hap09	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
A_japonica_AB038	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTAC	CATACGTAGG	GGACTCCTTA
A_luzonensis_AB4	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_australis_aust	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTG	TCAGCCGTCC	CATACATAGG	AAACTCCCTA
A_australis_schm	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTG	TCAGCCGTCC	CATACATAGG	AAACTCCCTA
A_bicolor_bicolo	TGAGGTGCCA	CAGTAATTAC	CAATCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_bicolor_pacifi	TGAGGTGCCA	CAGTAATTAC	CAATCTACTA	TCTGCCGTTC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTTACTA
A_malgumora_AP00	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACTTACTA	TCCGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AAACTCTCTA
A_celebesensis_A	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCCCTA
A_dieffenbachii_	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTAC	CATACGTAGG	AAACTCCCTA
A_interioris_AP0	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_marmorata_AP00	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_megastoma_AP00	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTGGG	AGACTCCCTA
A_mossambica_AP0	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCCCTA
A_labiata_AP0072	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCAGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_nebulosa_nebul	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCAGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_obscura_AP0072	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCCGTCC	CATATGTAGG	AGACTCACTA
A_reinhardtii_AP	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCCGCTGTCC	CATATGTAGG	GAACTCCCTA
A_rostrata_AP007	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAATCTATTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AAACTCCCTA
A_anguilla_KJ564	TGAGGTGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCCGTCC	CATATGTCGG	GAACTCCCTA
A_bengalensis_be	TGAGGCGCTA	CAGTAATTAC	CAACCTACTA	TCTGCAGTCC	CATACGTAGG	AGACTCACTA

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |

485 495 505 515 525 535

22eel02_Hap01	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel10_Hap02	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel03-04_Hap03	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel12_Hap04	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel05_08-09_11	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel16-17_Hap06	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel07_Hap07	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel01_Hap08	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
22eel06_Hap09	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_japonica_AB038	GTTCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_luzonensis_AB4	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GATAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_australis_aust	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_australis_schm	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_bicolor_bicolo	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGGGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA

A_bicolor_pacifi	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_malgumora_AP00	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	ATTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_celebesensis_A	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACTCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_dieffenbachii_	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_interioris_AP0	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	ATTCTCAGTT	GATAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_marmorata_AP00	GTCCAATGAA	TTTGAGGAGG	CTTTTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_megastoma_AP00	GTACAGTGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCTA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_mossambica_AP0	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAATGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_labiata_AP0072	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_nebulosa_nebul	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_obscura_AP0072	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGAGG	CTTTTCAGTT	GACAACGCTA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_reinhardtii_AP	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_rostrata_AP007	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTTTCAGTC	GACAACGCCA	CATTGACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_anguilla_KJ564	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	ATTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CATTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA
A_bengalensis_be	GTCCAATGAA	TCTGAGGGGG	CTTCTCAGTT	GACAACGCCA	CACTAACCCG	ATTCTTCGCA

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |
545 555 565 575 585 595

22ee102_Hap01	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee110_Hap02	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee103-04_Hap03	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee112_Hap04	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee105_08-09_11	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee116-17_Hap06	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee107_Hap07	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee101_Hap08	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
22ee106_Hap09	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCaCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_japonica_AB038	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_luzonensis_AB4	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGTGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_australis_aust	TTCCACTTCC	TGTTCCCAT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGAGCTACAA	TACTTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_australis_schm	TTCCACTTCC	TGTTCCCAT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGAGCTACAA	TACTTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_bicolor_bicolo	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTGTTCCCTA
A_bicolor_pacifi	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTA
A_malgumora_AP00	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	CGTAGTTGCT	GGGGCCACAA	TACTCCACCT	CCTGTTCCCTC
A_celebesensis_A	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGTGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_dieffenbachii_	TTCCACTTCT	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCT	GGAGCTACAA	TAATTCATCT	CCTATTCCCTA
A_interioris_AP0	TTTCATTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_marmorata_AP00	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGTGCTACAA	TAATCCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_megastoma_AP00	TTTCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATCCACCT	CCTATTCCCTT

A_mossambica_AP0	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	CGTAGTCGCC	GGAGCAACAA	TGCTCCATCT	CCTATTCCCTT
A_labiata_AP0072	TTTCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTTCTC
A_nebulosa_nebul	TTTCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTTCTC
A_obscura_AP0072	TTCCATTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCT	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTTCTC
A_reinhardtii_AP	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTT
A_rostrata_AP007	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTCGCC	GGGGCCACAA	TGCTTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_anguilla_KJ564	TTCCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCT	GGAGCCACAA	TACTTCACCT	CCTATTCCCTC
A_bengalensis_be	TTTCACTTCC	TATTTCCATT	TGTAGTTGCC	GGCGCTACAA	TAATTCACCT	CCTATTTCTC

....|....||....||....||....||....||....|

605 615 625 635 645 655

22ee102_Hap01	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee110_Hap02	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	aATCCCATTT
22ee103-04_Hap03	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee112_Hap04	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee105_08-09_11	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee116-17_Hap06	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee107_Hap07	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee101_Hap08	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
22ee106_Hap09	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
A_japonica_AB038	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	GATCCCATTT
A_luzonensis_AB4	CATGAAACAG	GGTCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAATTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTT
A_australis_aust	CACGAAACTG	GATCTAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_australis_schm	CACGAAACTG	GATCTAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_bicolor_bicolo	CACGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGG	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_bicolor_pacifi	CACGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_malgumora_AP00	CACGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_celebesensis_A	CATGAAACAG	GATCGAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_dieffenbachii_	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAGCAA	TCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	AGTCCCATTC
A_interioris_AP0	CATGAAACAG	GGTCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_marmorata_AP00	CATGAAACAG	GGTCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTGAACTCCG	ACGCGGACAA	AATTCATTC
A_megastoma_AP00	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_mossambica_AP0	CACGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	TCCAGTAGGA	CTAAATTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_labiata_AP0072	CATGAAACAG	GGTCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_nebulosa_nebul	CATGAAACAG	GGTCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTGAACTCTG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_obscura_AP0072	CACGAGACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTT
A_reinhardtii_AP	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	CTGAACTCTG	ATGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_rostrata_AP007	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCAGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC
A_anguilla_KJ564	CATGAAACAG	GATCAAACAA	CCCGTAGGA	TTAAACTCCG	ACGCAGACAA	AATCCCATTC

A_bengalensis_be CATGAAACAG GGTCAAACAA CCCAGTAGGA TTGAACTCTG ACGCAGACAA AATCCCATTC

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... | |.... |

665 675 685 695 705 715

22ee102_Hap01 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee110_Hap02 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee103-04_Hap03 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGaTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee112_Hap04 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee105_08-09_11 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee116-17_Hap06 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TtATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee107_Hap07 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee101_Hap08 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
22ee106_Hap09 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_japonica_AB038 CACCCTTATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_luzonensis_AB4 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGGTTTATTA TTATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_australis_aust CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTGCTA GGCTTCATTA TTATACTCAC CGCCCTAACA
A_australis_schm CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTGCTA GGCTTCATTA TTATACTCAC CGCCCTAACA
A_bicolor_bicolo CATCCATACT TCTCATACAA AGACCTGTTA GGATTCATTA TTATACTAAC TGCCCTAACA
A_bicolor_pacifi CATCCATACT TCTCATACAA AGACCTATTA GGATTCATTA TTATGCTAAC TGCCCTAACA
A_malgumora_AP00 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTTATTA TCATACTCAC CGCCCTAACG
A_celebesensis_A CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTATTA GGATTCATTA TTATACTGAC CGCCCTAACA
A_dieffenbachii_ CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TTATACTCAC CGCCCTAACA
A_interioris_AP0 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTTATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_marmorata_AP00 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTGCTA GGATTCATTA TCATACTAAC CGCCTTAACA
A_megastoma_AP00 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATCA TCATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_mossambica_AP0 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTTTTA GGGTTCATTA TTATACTCAC CGCCCTAACA
A_labiata_AP0072 CATCCATACT TCTCTTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TTATATTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_nebulosa_nebul CATCCATACT TCTCTTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TTATATTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_obscura_AP0072 CACCATACT TCTCATACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TTATACTAAC CGCCCTAACA
A_reinhardtii_AP CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTGCTA GGATTCATTA TTATACTAAC CGCTTAAACA
A_rostrata_AP007 CACCATATT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TCATGCTCAC CGCTCTAACA
A_anguilla_KJ564 CACCATACT TCTCCTACAA AGACCTACTG GGGTTCATTA TCATGCTCAC CGCCCTAACA
A_bengalensis_be CATCCATACT TCTCTTACAA AGACCTACTA GGATTCATTA TTATATTAAC CGCCCTAACA

.... |.... | |.... | |.... | |....

725 735 745 755

22ee102_Hap01 ATACTTGCCC TATTCTCCCC AAACCTCCTT GGGGA+CCA
22ee110_Hap02 ATACTTGCCC TATTCTCCCC AAACCTCCTT GGGGA+CCA
22ee103-04_Hap03 ATACTTGCCC TATTCTCCCC AAACCTCCTT GGGGA+CCA

22ee112_Hap04	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGACCCA
22ee105_08-09_11	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGAtCCA
22ee116-17_Hap06	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGAtCCA
22ee107_Hap07	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGAtCCA
22ee101_Hap08	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGAtCCA
22ee106_Hap09	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGAtCCA
A_japonica_AB038	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTCCCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGGGATCCA
A_luzonensis_AB4	ATACTTGCTC	TATTCTATCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_australis_aust	ATACTTGCCC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_australis_schm	ATACTTGCCC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_bicolor_bicolo	ATACTTGCTC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTTCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_bicolor_pacifi	TTACTTGCTC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_malgumora_AP00	ATACTTGCCC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_celebesensis_A	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTACCC	AAATCTTCTT	GGAGATCCA
A_dieffenbachii_	ATACTTGCCC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGATCCA
A_interioris_AP0	ATACTTGCTC	TATTCTATCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_marmorata_AP00	ATACTTGCTC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_megastoma_AP00	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTTCTC	GGAGACCCA
A_mossambica_AP0	ATACTGCCCC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTACTC	GGAGACCCA
A_labiata_AP0072	ATACTTGCTC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGATCCA
A_nebulosa_nebul	ATACTTGCTC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGATCCA
A_obscura_AP0072	ATACTTGCTC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_reinhardtii_AP	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_rostrata_AP007	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTACCC	CAACCTGCTT	GGTGATCCA
A_anguilla_KJ564	ATACTTGCCC	TATTCTACCC	GAACCTGCTT	GGAGACCCA
A_bengalensis_be	ATACTTGCTC	TATTTTACCC	AAACCTCCTT	GGAGATCCA